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The Role of the Mass Media in Developing Sport Tourism in the Province of Isfahan

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Abstract: The present study was carried out with the aim of determining the role of the mass media in developing sport tourism in the province of Isfahan, Iran. The participants in the study includes all the managers and employees in Cultural Heritage and Tourism Organization and travel agencies (N=2000) among whom 350 were selected using Cochran's formula and random sampling method. The questionnaire consisted of 45 items in form of three factors. After establishing the face and content validity of the questionnaire, the construct validity of that was also investigated through exploratory factor analysis (EFA). In order to determine the reliability of the data collection tool, the Cronbach Alpha was sued and a reliability coefficient of 0.812 was obtained. The results obtained from the Friedman's analysis of the variance suggested a significant difference among the roles of the different types of media in improving sport tourism in Isfahan.

Keywords: Isfahan; The mass media; Sport tourism

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